

EFFICACY OF BHANT (CLERODENDRUM INFORMTUNATUM LINN.) IN KHALITYA (ALOPECIA)

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INTRODUCTION

Among the common therapeutic problems are probably a few ones that challenge the ill and ingenuity of the dermatologists more than that done by Alopecia areata which is mostly resistant to treatment so far known to the medical world. The present known treatment and management is still not less effective and with side effects.

The treatment known does not work effectively in many cases and even in those where they work the relapses are very common and frequent, Due to these drawbacks they can not be recommended as satisfactory routine treatment of Alopecia areata. Thus it is obvious that an ideal treatment for the cure and relief of Alopecia areata remains unknown.

The above mentioned situation presses the need of further research on the problem of treatment and management of Alopecia areata. With this idea and the indication of a large

number of single or compound topical drugs of herbal, mineral and animal origin in the samhitas of Indian system of medicine (Ayurveda) in the form of tailas and lepas, for the

treatment of Alopecia areata with claims of satisfactory results by Ayurvedic physicians, this scientific therapeutic study was planned. In this therapeutic study the validity and the potentialities of pharmaceutical preparation ‘‘Bhant’s Oil’ is planned in A.A.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The subjects included in this therapeutic trial were from the O. P. D. All the patients who were diagnosed as a case of Alopecia areata were subjected to this therapeutic study.

The diagnosis in every patient included in the study was made on the clinical grounds. In addition to history and the clinical examination, appropriate laboratory procedures were undertaken to exclude systemic disease. This therapeutic study is based on total 33 cases who could continue treatment were followed till the end of the followup. The Patients who could not turn up after one week for follow-up study, are not included in this study.

Trial Drug

For the therapeutic trial in this study, the leaves of the plant ‘‘Bhantas’’ was used. Out of the leaves an oil was Prepared, which was used topically on the lesions of Alopecia areata.

Pharmaceutical preparation of Bhantas oil

The leaves of Bhantas were chopped in small pieces and were Compressed for the extraction of their juice. About 20 kg. of fresh juice was collected and processed for the preparation of oil, fer which 5 kg. of tila oil was used.

First of all the til-oil was put on the fire into a pan and was heated to make it free from any content Of water. Afterwards the total 20 kg of fresh juice was intermixed with the oil and was kept on boiling on moderate heat. Still further onefourth of the weight of the oil. The kalka of Bhantas was also mixed into the boiling oil, which was constantly being stirred with laddle. Thus the process of providing moderate heat to the oil was maintained for three successive days.

The oil was taken off from the fire when it reached to the stage of madhyama degree of sneha-paka. The following tests were applied to see the perfectness of the madhya paka of the prepared oil

1. The oil was dropping off entirely free from its drugs, which became dry and shapeless.
2. The oil was found non sticky and frothless.

3. The drop of oil after putting into the fire burnt without any sound. The colour of oil became greenish.

The above mentioned criteria when became positive, only then the oil was considered perfectly prepared.

Criteria of Assessment

1. The main criteria of assessment of the therapeutic trial was based on the regrowth of the hair on the lesions, which was clinically photographed for records to be used at the time of final assessment.
2. Next criteria of assessment was the Satisfaction reported by the patients after total Period of treatment. The results of this therapeutic study were recorded as follows in terms of improvement.

Cured: Complete regrowth of the hairs on the lesions.

Improved: Regrowth of the hairs on the maximum area of the lesions barring some of the total area of the lesion or lesions.

Deteriorated: Increased in the number of lesions and in the area of existing lesion or lesions.

RESULTS

Out of the total 33 cases included in therapeutic trial most of them (87.88%) have shown improvement, of lesser or greater degree and those who have shown improvement, amongst them 54.55% have been completely cured, while only rest 33.33% were labelled as improved. Only 12.12% of the total cases could not show any improvement in their clinical condition and they remained stationary, but even they have not shown any deterioration during the period of Six months of the treatment, which is sufficiently a long time for further development of the disease, considering the area of the existing lesion or lesions or in their number.

DISCUSSION

In this therapeutic investigation, total 33 cases of alopecia areata were included out of these 54.55 percent have been labelled as cured and 33.33 percent showed improvement in their clinical condition of lesser or greater degree and rest 12.12 percent cases remained stationary but even these cases could not show any extension in their disease, considering the area of the

brain or lesions or their number. From this therapeutic result, it can be inferred that the drug “bhanta” is useful in the treatment of alopecia areata of any specific type which is caused due to some specific etiology only and it can not be claimed better for all types of cases. All these cases who showed encouraging results might have been caused by one and the same etiology, therefore they showed good results and others who might have been due to another etiology could not show any result or only some improvement, in which this drug may not have similar effect.

Under these circumstances now it remains to find out that on which specific type of etiology this drug acts and on which it is not, In view of the limitations of our knowledge of the etiology it is well to change from one form of treatment to another, if the first proves unsuccessful. Now it has become necessary, seeing the results of this study, to plan another investigation to find out ‘the exact etiological factor where this drug acts, as it was used on purely empirical basis without any pre-idea of destroying an infectious agent, acting on a possible endocrine’ disturbance of reflex irritation.

The oil of “bhanta” is the medicament of choice for stimulating the scalp. The plan of treatment with this oil “bhanta” is as follows : Vigorous massage of the plaque with a mixture of equal parts of the oil of “bhanta” (deodorised), lanolin or baseline each and night application of the same mixture to healthy portions of the scalp atleast two or three times weekly even every night in severe cases. Cleanse the scalp next morning with a solution of thirty grams of acetone containig one gram of glacial acetic acid. Then shampoo the entire scalp with tar soap if the patient is engaged in a daily occupation. If he remains at home a shampoo is necessary only once weekly.

General tonic treatment : Sufficient sleep, fresh air, and Outdoor exercise are not to be forgotten.

The cure and improvement results of this therapeutic study can be assumed to have resulted from this form of indiscriminate therapy. It is not to be forgotten that quite a large number of cases of ordinary alopecia areata of the scalp will 'clear up eventually without any treatment whatever.

CONCLUSION

The Indian indigenous drug bhant (*Clerodendron infortunatum* Linn.) of herbal origin in the form of bhates-oil is effective for the treatment of khalitya (alopecia areata).

The indigenous drugs tried, are safe to use for pretty long time with no untoward effect.***